

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

COL11A1 (collagen type XI alpha 1 chain)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	1301 / P12107
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD, AMP-AD
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Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
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CONTENTS OF TEP

Bioinformatic analysis: Target source & hypothesis

Protein constructs & expression methods: protein constructs for baculovirus expression for structure determination and in vitro assays.

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 3.74 (rank #978, 96.1th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 3.74 out of 5 (rank #978, 96.1th percentile). The individual score components include 1.90 of 3 for genetics, and 1.84 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of COL11A1 protein is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. COL11A1 is annotated to GO terms from the Structural Stabilization, Proteostasis, and Metal Binding and Homeostasis domains.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins.

Overall	rank	pctl	GeneticsScore	OmicsScore
3.741	978	96.08	1.903	1.838

The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of expression. The expression of COL11A1 is confidently detected in oligodendrocyte precursor cells (OPC) as well as both excitatory and inhibitory neuron sub-types within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

COL11A1 is a subunit of heterotrimeric fibrillar collagen (1) that is developmentally associated with cartilage formation (2-4), but has also been observed in expressions studies of brain as well (5, 6). COL11A1 was identified within our work as part of a proteomic module tightly associated with cognitive impairment and AD pathology in human brain studies (7). The mechanism of interaction is not known, and future investigations will be required. Toward that end, we have developed a set of resources within the COL11A1 target enablement package (TEP) which includes purified protein, validated antibody, and a full bioinformatic characterization of COL11A1 discussed above. We hope that these resources will help the scientific community in future investigations of the association between COL11A1 and AD.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

COL11A1, collagen type XI alpha 1 chain, is a fibrillar form of collagen primarily involved in the formation of the extracellular matrix (ECM) in cartilage(4). It forms heterotypic fibrils with other collagen types, such as type II and type IX, contributing to the structural integrity and function of cartilage(1). Its triple-helical structure consists of three alpha chains wound around each other, characterized by a Gly-X-Y repeating sequence where X and Y are often proline and hydroxyproline, ensuring the stability of the triple helix(1, 2, 8). COL11A1 also contains N-terminal and C-terminal propeptides involved in fibril formation and interaction with other ECM components. Mutations in COL11A1 are associated with autosomal recessive forms of Stickler's Disease, an optic developmental disorder that can result in severe malformation of the eye(4).

The primary biological role of COL11A1 is in the proper formation and maintenance of cartilage during development and adulthood(1, 2, 8). It is a critical component in connective tissues, ensuring their structural integrity and proper function. While COL11A1 is crucial for cartilage, there is also some expression observed in brain, as noted by COL11A1 expression within the striatum(6), suggesting a structural role for COL11A1 in the extracellular matrix of neurons and central nervous system (CNS) tissue. COL11A1 expression was specifically noted in brain and oligodendrocytes within the Seattle AD single cell study (SEA-AD) of Alzheimer's disease expression patterns(5), and as demonstrated within the bioinformatics section of this report.

There is no direct evidence linking COL11A1 to neurodegenerative diseases generally, or AD specifically, other than expression patterns observed in SEA-AD study mentioned above and the seminal work that led to its investigation within TREAT-AD in which deep proteomic sequencing of large sets of brain bank samples identified the module containing COL11A1 to be most associated with changes in both cognitive decline and pathological progression(7). The mechanistic association with AD pathogenesis is unknown, but as an extracellular matrix protein, in close association with heparin and heparin-binding proteins, it may participate in the heparin associated proteomic linkage with AD(9). COL11A1 is reported to be involved in signaling pathways linking the kinase AKT and the transcription factor CREB to apoptotic evasion(10), a pathway that is also known to promote synaptic enhancement during learning and memory events(11-13). The mechanism of the AD association requires and warrants future investigation to better understand the role of COL11A1 fibrillar collagen chain in the AD pathogenic sequelae.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Proteins Purified

COL11A1_1570-1806_HisN-AviC: Baculovirus expression for structure determination

COL11A1_36-250_HisN_AviC: Baculovirus expression for structure determination

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further investigation of the role of COL11A1 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Proteins Expression and Purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

Gene name	COL11A1
Uniprot ID	P12107
Region	1570-1806

Description	May play an important role in fibrillogenesis by controlling lateral growth of collagen II fibrils.
Synonyms	Collagen alpha-1(XI) chain
Construct ID	COL11A1_1570-1806_HisN_AviC (PBC040G09)
Parental Vector	pFHMSP-AviN-LIC-N
Tag (N-terminal)	MKFLVNVALVFMVVYISYIAAAPEHHHHHDYDIPTTENLYFQGAMD
Tag (C-terminal)	SSKGGYGLNDIFEAQKIEWHE

Protein mass (with tag)	34830.03 Da
Extinction Coefficient with tag ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	53205
Protein sequence (with tag)	MKFLVNVALVFMVVYISYIAAAPEHHHHHDYDIPTTENLYFQGAMDLDYSDGME EIFGSLNSLKQDIEHMKFPMGTQTNPARTCKDLQLSHPDFPDGEYWIDPNQGCSG DSFKVYCNFTSGGETCIYDPKKSEGVRISWPKPKPGSWFSEFKRGKLLSYLDVE GNSINMVQMTFLKLLTASARQNFTYHCHQSAAWYDVSSGSYDKALRFLGSNDEEM SYDNNPFIKTLYDGCASRKGYEKTVIEINTPKIDQVPIVDVMINDFGDQNQKFGF EVGPVCF LGSSKGGYGLNDIFEAQKIEWHE

Purified Protein	
IMAC, Ni (step 1): COL11A1_1570-1806_Hi sN_AViC	
GF S200 26/60 (step 2): COL11A1_1570-1806_Hi sN_AViC	
Intact Mass Deconvolution:	N/A
Observed Mass:	N/A
Protein yield:	20.4 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	Insect cells: Sf9 (<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>)
Expression Medium	I-Max Insect Media W/ L-Glutamine, Wisent Biocentre
Transformation and storage	The baculovirus expression vector system (BEVS), specifically Bac-to-Bac Expression System (Invitrogen), employing <i>Autographa californica</i> multiple nucleopolyhedrovirus (AcMNPV) has been used for expression screening and production of target protein. The plasmid transfer vector containing the gene of interest was transformed into DH10Bac <i>E. coli</i> competent cells to generate recombinant viral bacmid DNA. Adherent Sf9 cells were then transfected with bacmid DNA to generate recombinant viruses used for the baculovirus-mediated production in the insect cells.

Expression	For the scale-up productions, suspension cultures of the baculovirus-infected insect cells, (SCBIIIC) were prepared by infection of the Sf9 cells with the corresponding P2 viruses. On the day of production, 2 L of Sf9 cells (cell viability > 97%) in 2.5 L Tunair shake flasks or 4 L in 5 L reagent bottles were diluted to a cell density of 4×10^6 /mL. These cells were infected directly with 10-12 mL/L of suspension culture of baculovirus-infected insect cells and incubated at a lowered temperature of 25 °C, at 145 rpm. Infected cells' density and viability along with the cell sizes monitored after 72 hours post-infection time to be able to collect cells for purification at the optimal conditions when Sf9 cells are well infected, usually in 5-6 days after the post-infection time.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 250 mM imidazole 3. SEC buffer: 20 mM HEPES (pH 7.4), 300 mM NaCl, 2mM TCEP 4. IEC buffer: 20 mM HEPES (pH 7.4), 260 mM NaCl, 2mM TCEP 5. TALON beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Spin down cells @6500RPM for 15min 2. Transfer each 1.5L supernatant to a 2.8L flask with 150ml 10X PBS. 3. Add (2ml/L) Ni-sepharose beads to the supernatant and shake at 100RPM at 18 °C for 60 min. 4. Transfer the supernatant + beads to an open column to collect the beads and keep the flowthrough. 5. Wash beads with 50CV of lysis buffer. 6. Elute protein with 5CV elution buffer. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay. 7. Add beads (2ml /L) to the collected flowthrough for second binding same condition and repeat the same wash and elution after 1hour shaking.
Purification step 2: Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 26/60 column in SEC buffer at 3 ml/min. 2. Analyze fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity for next step.

Gene name	COL11A1
Uniprot ID	P12107
Region	36-250

Description	May play an important role in fibrillogenesis by controlling lateral growth of collagen II fibrils.
Synonyms	Collagen alpha-1(XI) chain
Construct ID	COL11A1_36-250_HisN_AviC (PBC040G07)
Parental Vector	pFHMSP-AviC-LIC-N
Tag (N-terminal)	MKFLVNVALVFMVVYISYIYAAAPEHHHHHHHDYDIPTTENLYFQGAMD
Tag (C-terminal)	SSKGGYGLNDIFEAQKIEWHE
Protein mass (with tag)	31798.95 Da
Extinction Coefficient with tag ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	28880
Protein sequence (with tag)	MKFLVNVALVFMVVYISYIYAAAPEHHHHHHHDYDIPTTENLYFQGAMDAAPVDVLK ALDFHNSPEGISKTTGFCTNRKNSKGSDTAYRVSKQAQLSAPTKQLFPGGTFPEDFSIL FTVKPKKGIQSFLLSIYNEHGIIQQIGVEVGRSPVFLFEDHTGKPAPEDYPLFRTVNIAD GKWHRVAISVEKKTVMIVDCKKKTKPLDRSERAIVDTNGITVFGTRILDEEVFEGDI QQFLITGDPKAAAYDYCEHYSPPDCDSSAPKASSKGGYGLNDIFEAQKIEWHE

Purified Protein	
IMAC, Ni (step 1): COL11A1_36-250_ HisN_AviC	<p>8L culture, 2ml beads for each L and each run 20 Tris 8.0 500 NaCl 5% glycerol/250 imidazole 4.6mg/ml 2.3mg 50ul/tubeX10</p> <p>from n2: 4.4mg/ml, 1.76mg 50ul/tubeX7</p>
Intact Mass Deconvolution:	N/A
Observed Mass:	N/A
Protein yield:	0.5 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	Insect cells: Sf9 (<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>)
Expression Medium	I-Max Insect Media W/ L-Glutamine, Wisent Biocentre
Transformation and storage	The baculovirus expression vector system (BEVS), specifically Bac-to-Bac Expression System (Invitrogen), employing <i>Autographa californica</i> multiple nucleopolyhedrovirus (AcMNPV) has been used for expression screening and production of target protein. The plasmid transfer vector containing the gene of interest was transformed into DH10Bac <i>E. coli</i> competent cells to generate recombinant viral bacmid DNA. Adherent Sf9 cells were then transfected with bacmid DNA to generate recombinant viruses used for the baculovirus-mediated production in the insect cells.

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Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 250 mM imidazole 3. Final buffer: 20mM Tris pH8.0, 250mM NaCl 2mM TCEP 1,2-propanediol 4. Nickel beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Spin down cells @6500RPM for 15min 2. Transfer each 1.5L supernatant to a 2.8L flask with 150ml 10X PBS. 3. Add (2ml/L) Ni-sepharose beads to the supernatant and shake at 100RPM at 18 °C for 60 min. 4. Transfer the supernatant + beads to an open column to collect the beads and keep the flowthrough. 5. Wash beads with 50CV of lysis buffer. 6. Elute protein with 5CV elution buffer. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay. 7. Add beads (2ml /L) to the collected flowthrough for second binding same condition and repeat the same wash and elution after 1hour shaking.

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